

reSEARCH-EU

DISSEMINATION MATERIAL AND DATABASE

DELIVERABLE 7.2

(DUE TO M36, December 2023)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017454

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1. Introduction

The aim of this work has been to ensure good communication and dissemination of results through different media, materials and formats of the research eu project, internally among partners, but also to a general public with an external communication plan.

On the one hand, for the internal communication of the project, different communication tools have been used, taking the SEA-EU internal communication system as a model. The communication tools and channels have been: The reSEArch-EU document-sharing platform (Alfresco) and Mailing lists created in order to increase the efficiency of message sharing among participants of different working groups: Extended EC, reSEArch-EU TWG, Quality and Ethics and Inter-Project Coordination Committee.

On the other hand, the quintuple-helix approach has been taken into account for external communication, which inspires the entire Project. Since it aims to have an impact on academia, business, public institutions, the environment and civil society, the reSEArch-EU communication strategy established channels intended to address all of these.

Finally, to ensure the effectiveness of the communication strategy all the activities were quantified using performance indicators and measurement tools. The annex at table 1 shows a list of both the performance indicators and the measurement tools implemented for each WP.

2. Identification of the work name

Deliverable No. and Title	Deliverable: D7.2 DISSEMINATION MATERIAL AND DATABASE
Leader	Prof. M. Laura Martín Díaz (UCA)
Related task(s)	Task 7.1; 7.2; 7.3
Authors	Prof. M. Laura Martín Díaz Mariia Iamkovaia Beatriz Díaz Garduño
Dissemination level	Public report
Due submission date	22/12/23
Submission	05/12/23
Project number	101017454
Start date of project	01/01/2021
Duration	36 months
D7.2 - Dissemination material and database (reports, white papers, newsletter, videos, webinars, posters, brochures, press releases, end project documentary)	

3. Expectations at the beginning of the project

The communication strategy of reSEArch-EU

3.1. Internal communication among partners

Principles

The reSEArch-EU Project inherits the internal communications system created for the SEA-EU Alliance.

Three general principles will be applied in order to achieve an optimal internal communications system:

- Security and efficiency in internal communication by virtual means will be the founding principles that will guide the implementation and use of all communication means.

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- Partners will avoid any virtual means that do not ensure integrity and confidentiality of the data shared among project partners, and non-proprietary software will be the preferred option for the implementation of any solutions.
- The use of the SEA-EU brand image will not only extend to public documents, but also to all documents shared among project partners.

The reSEArch-EU Project will also make use of different communication tools taking the internal communication system of SEA-EU as a model. Therefore, these will be the channels for internal communication:

- The reSEArch-EU document-sharing platform (Alfresco). Following established principles in the SEA-EU Alliance, this platform shall make use of non-proprietary software if possible; data will be stored in safe servers of the coordinating partner and their organization.
- Mailing lists. They have been created in order to increase the efficiency of message sharing among participants of different working groups:
 - Extended EC SEA-EU Executive committee
 - Research vice-rectors
 - reSEArchEu WP leaders
 - CC: reSEArch-EU TWG
 - reSEArch-EU TWG
 - Quality and Ethics SEA-EU quality list CC: reSEArch-EU TWG, Inter-Project Coordination Committee.

3.2. External communication: dissemination channels and stakeholder engagement

The formulation of the communication strategy for the reSEArch-EU Project takes into account the quintuple-helix approach that inspires the entire Project. Since it aims to have an impact on academia, business, public institutions, the environment and civil society, the reSEArch-EU communication strategy will establish channels intended to address all of these.

The webpage of the Project, hosted within the SEA-EU Alliance website, along with the Alliance's social media accounts and the public events organized, are at the core of the communication strategy. Then, scientific publications, policy briefs, newsletters, press releases and video capsules will reach, respectively though not exclusively, each stakeholder.

3.3. Expected KPIs for external communication

The effectiveness of the communication strategy in the reSEArch-EU Project will be quantified using performance indicators and measurement tools.

4. Development of the work

The communication work of the reSEArch EU project has been carried out following the initial communication strategy for each type of communication: internal and external. In addition, its effectiveness has been measured at all times, especially for external communications.

Specifically, for external communications, a **gradual procedure** has been followed, with the idea that the audience became familiar with our way of communicating and the different formats and channels that they could find information about the project. The established procedure, in general, is as follows:

- First of all, a news piece is published on the reSEArch EU website.
- Once the news is published, the link is disseminated in social networks with the idea that the public can always expand information on our website and thus get more visits to show the project.
- Finally, on a quarterly or monthly basis, subscribers have been informed through the SEA EU newsletter.

However, depending on the type of information, this procedure has been adapted in order to communicate the message of the project in the best way possible.

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On the other hand, in addition to the digital dissemination that has been done about the project, these actions have been accompanied by public events and multiple activities open to the general public, in the different Universities of the Alliance such as the European Researchers Night (ERN) or Science Activities in a relaxed atmosphere.

5. Methodology

To carry out this communication strategy, different elements and channels were available at the service of the project.

5.1 Webpage of the Project

The webpage of the Project is hosted within the SEA-EU Alliance website but it has its own domain and identity. In this sense the reSEArch EU website has been a crucial tool for communication for the following reasons:

- Dissemination of Information: the website allows the project to share the news, activities, resources and results with the audience following the quintuple-helix model (academia, business, public institutions, the environment and civil society) in an easily accessible format.
- Collaboration: Websites can facilitate collaboration between researchers, stakeholders or other audiences sharing work, get feedback, and even find potential collaborators for future projects.
- Transparency: By sharing methodologies, data, and results in order to increase trust, proximity and equity.
- Outreach: the website helps to reach a wider audience like the general public, policy makers, etc. It can also help to make the research more understandable to non-experts.
- Longevity and Accessibility: Unlike traditional forms of publishing, a website can make a research project's findings accessible long after the project has ended. It also allows for the inclusion of different types of media, like videos, and to have all the information updated easily.

As a summary, the website could enhance the visibility, impact, and longevity of reSEArch EU project.

5.2 Social Media Accounts

The organization of the social media accounts of the project have had **two stages**.

The first year and a half of the project, all **social media accounts were shared** with the SEA EU project. However, as more content was generated (results, events, activities) totally focused on the research, the need was seen to differentiate the communication and accounts (on the general social networks such as **Instagram and Facebook**) due to the different audiences to which each project was directed.

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In this way, reSEArch EU social media accounts could focus on reaching a target audience that is 100% interested in everything related to research. Although part of the materials have been continued sharing with the Alliance's social media accounts Twitter and LinkedIn networks, where the algorithm is less demanding.

The idea was to continue increasing and improving the communication of the two projects, without modifying the preferences of the current audience or damaging the reach and other factors that influence the positioning and views of the content with the algorithm.

Apart from this two stages, Social media can play a significant role in a research project for several reasons:

- **Data Collection:** Social media platforms provide a wealth of data for the project team about the audience: demographics, behaviors, and interactions.
- **Recruitment:** Project team can use social media to recruit participants for activities, studies or surveys. It can be a cost-effective way to reach a large and diverse audience all over the world.
- **Dissemination:** Social media is used to share all the activities, events, results, resources, etc of the project with a broad audience.
- **Engagement:** Social media allows project team to engage with academia, business, public institutions, the environment and civil society. This can include the possibility of communicating directly, answering questions, receiving feedback, and fostering discussions about the project.
- **Networking:** Social media can help researchers connect with other experts in their field or other complementaries. This can lead to collaborations and the sharing of ideas.
- **Monitoring Impact:** Social media metrics can be used by the project team to track the reach and impact of the work.

In conclusion, social media can be a powerful tool for reSEArch EU project in order to collect data, participant recruitment, dissemination of results, audience engagement, professional networking or impact monitoring.

5.3 Newsletter

Due to the applications and objectives of the newsletters format, the project team decided to share the regular newsletter with that of the SEA EU Alliance, from the beginning.

In this sense, the information that reSEArch EU project needed to transmit was published through this common newsletter that was first published quarterly and from SEA EU 2.0 (January 2023) they decided to change it to monthly.

Moreover, newsletters play a crucial role in research projects for several reasons:

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- **Communication:** Newsletters are an effective way to communicate updates and findings to all members involved in the project: researchers, stakeholders involved, students, society and any other interested parties subscribed.
- **Engagement:** Regular newsletters keep everyone engaged and informed about the progress of the project. This can help maintain interest and support for the project over time.
- **Transparency:** By sharing the process and results through newsletters, research projects can demonstrate transparency. This can enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the project.
- **Record Keeping:** Newsletters can serve as a record of the project's progress. They can be referred back to for information or used as a part of the project's documentation.

Therefore, the newsletter is a versatile and valuable tool for enhancing communication, engagement, transparency and record keeping for reSEArch EU.

5.4 Broadcast Channel - YouTube - Video Capsules and webinars

Having a broadcast channel like YouTube for reSEArch EU project can be highly beneficial for disseminating webinars, video capsules and other online activities. There are multiple reasons to have a YouTube channel:

- **Reach:** YouTube has over 2 billion logged-in users each month. This vast user base can help your research project reach a global audience.
- **Accessibility:** YouTube videos can be accessed anytime, anywhere, and on any device that has an internet connection. This makes it easy for interested individuals to engage with your content at their convenience.
- **Engagement:** YouTube's features such as likes, comments, and shares enable interaction with the audience. This can foster a community around the project, encouraging more engagement and discussion.
- **Visibility:** Videos on YouTube are indexed by search engines, making them discoverable to people searching for related content. Proper use of titles, descriptions, and tags can further enhance your content's visibility.
- **Multimedia Presentation:** YouTube allows for multimedia content, combining visuals, sound, and text. This can make complex research topics more understandable and engaging.
- **Archiving:** YouTube can serve as an archive for all the webinars and online activities, making it easy for anyone to access previous content.

Then, a YouTube channel can significantly enhance the dissemination and impact of your research project, making your webinars and online activities accessible and engaging to a global audience.

On the other hand, the team project choses to share the YouTube channel with that of SEA EU Alliance to multiply our reach and efforts and make content consumption easier for our entire audience.

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5.5 Public events organized: workshops, webinars and science citizen activities

Additionally to all the digital channels to disseminate our results and resources, organizing public events about citizen science activities is of great importance for several reasons:

- **Community Engagement:** Public events provide an opportunity for the community to engage with the research project. This can foster a sense of ownership and involvement among community members, which can lead to increased support for the project.
- **Knowledge dissemination:** These events serve as a platform to disseminate knowledge about the project, its results and available resources
- **Promotion:** Public events can help in promoting the project to a wider audience. This can attract more participants, sponsors, and other stakeholders to the project.
- **Networking:** These events provide a platform for networking with other researchers, potential collaborators, and stakeholders. This can lead to new partnerships and opportunities for future projects.

Then, scientific publications, policy briefs, newsletters, press releases and video capsules will reach, respectively though not exclusively, each stakeholder.

6. Challenges identified and solutions proposed

The main difficulties faced during the dissemination materials and database were to coordinate the reception of the information from each University of the Alliance. The dissemination channels and protocols are not the same in each University. In this sense reSEArch EU project needs to create its own procedure and establish it little by little.

The information was received through the technicians by email and the communication officer transformed in the different formats depending on each communication channel.

Another big challenge was present with the language and audience that the project wanted to reach with our material in each case. The official language of the project is English. However, none of the universities participating in the project have English as their native language and therefore, neither do the citizens of each site.

Therefore, when we wanted to disseminate activities, resources or results aimed at the general population, we were faced with the language barrier in terms of the scope of communication.

To overcome these drawbacks, we resorted to local communication channels, from each university, so that they could make the dissemination in the native language of each city and thus achieve our goal: to involve the ideal audience in each case.

7. Results obtained - External communication actions: dissemination channels and stakeholder engagement

7.1 Webpage of the Project

The webpage of the Project: <https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/> is hosted within the SEA-EU Alliance website.

The web page presents a menu divided into 9 categories. These categories in turn correspond to two orders.

On the one hand we have 5 tabs that correspond to the tasks and materials that have been created in the work packages (WP).

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The rest of the tabs correspond to the categories where the information “about us”, “the agenda”, “the results” and the “news & events” are explained.

This order is designed so that people who participate or are involved in the project can consult all the information they need about it.

On the other hand, the home page is ordered in such a way that any person involved in the project or not can consult the information, results and resources of the project in a

very intuitive way. In the first place we find the highlights and the latest news of the project with the most useful and important resources for visitors. In the next block, we find 4 images and each one corresponds to a target audience we are addressing with the project: researchers, students and entrepreneurs, companies and society in general.

Each block has a directory of resources and activities to consult depending on the interest of the audience.

For Society

Figure caption of the society block from the homepage as an example of the categories

This home page ends with a gallery of videos that have been created in the project, the contact of each university belonging to the project and a calendar of activities.

As for the 5 tabs corresponding to the activities including in each work packages, the relations are:

- Anti-fragility - regarding WP2: Increasing resilience and anti-fragility of research and innovation.
- Innovation - regarding WP3: Bridging the gap with the innovation ecosystem.
- Co-Creation - regarding WP4: Co-designing, co-creating and co-delivering for knowledge democratization.
- Open Science regarding WP5: Building an open future: fostering open science across the SEA-EU community and beyond.
- SEA EU Talent - regarding WP7: Dissemination.

Regarding the results tab, all the deliverables are available to consult all the reports:

Project results

Name	Description	Leader	Completion
Project Handbook	Guidelines for the successful implementation of the project, including management bodies, quality assurance mechanisms and decision making procedures.	University of Cadiz	March 2021
Data Management Plan	Overview of the policies implemented in reSEArch-EU regarding collection, storing, sharing and publication of research data produced in the project.	University of Cadiz	June 2021
Ethics Self-Assessment	Identification of all the ethical issues that may appear in the implementation of reSEArch-EU and how project partners plan to deal with them.	University of Cadiz	June 2021
Report on best practices in open science	Summary of the results obtained in the survey on current practices in open science shared with all project partners.	University of Malta	September 2021
Report on stakeholder engagement strategies	Analysis of the main strategies adopted by the six partner universities to engage with society in projects with a certain degree of co-creation with the civil society.	Kiel University	December 2021
Inter-Alliance Cooperation Agreement with EU-CONEXUS	This Agreement establishes the terms and conditions under which collaboration between the Parties will be conducted, as well as the methodology, structures and procedures that will be put in place to allow for mutual learning and common understanding.	University of Cadiz	December 2021 (first version)

Figure caption of the results tab

Here is the link directly to the results page:

<https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/project-deliverables/>

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7.1.1 Principal achievements with the webpage

The reSEArch-EU website had 26.352 page views from January 2023 to November 2023, 673.3.7 K of backlinks and 2.5K keywords positioned in Google.

7.1.2 Challenges identify and proposal solutions with the webpage

As mentioned earlier in the document, the reSEArch EU site is hosted on the SEA EU Alliance website. This has had advantages in terms of positioning and unity of the projects, among others. However, it has also meant having certain limitations and disadvantages which are detailed below.

As the website was designed for the SEA EU project, and the theme and configuration were chosen and predetermined, there was no possibility of tracking the number of visits or number of downloads for each of our documents or deliverables as the KPIs had demanded.

On the other hand, the team project was faced with a big challenge at the end of our project, since the SEA EU 1.0 project ended in December 2022 and was renewed in its SEA EU 2.0 version.

In this new version of SEA EU 2.0 a new website is contemplated to overcome the problems that had been detected in SEA EU 1.0 but it will also mean that our website will be migrated and will undergo some important changes that will have an impact on the statistics and monitoring in the medium and long term.

In fact, one of the main problems we encountered is that when SEA EU migrated its new website in July 2023, we lost all the statistics and many backlinks that were already indexed and positioned.

In this sense, we have done everything in our power to fix the routes on our website and complement the statistics data that we had achieved until then with the new counters from the date of migration.

With these manual corrections, thanks to all the periodic reports that have been made throughout the project, we have been able to rescue real statistics of the number of visits to the page throughout the project, despite not being able to track all the KPIs independently for each section of the website and the download of each document.

7.2 Social Media Accounts

The significance of social media in the research-EU project is very important in the context of our Alliance of Universities since it promotes collaboration and quality among higher education institutions across Europe.

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The project reSEArch-EU has the following individual social media accounts:

- Instagram: <https://instagram.com/researcheu/>
- Facebook: [researcheu | Facebook](https://www.facebook.com/researcheu)

The social media accounts of reSEArch-EU shared with the SEA-EU project are:

- X (Twitter): <https://twitter.com/SeaEuAlliance>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/seaeualliance/>

The content published corresponds to all the activities, results and resources that have been created within the framework of the reSEArch EU project.

<p>Example of deliverable materials for Social Media</p>	<p>Example of webinar announcement for Social Media</p>	<p>Examples of participation in face to face activities</p>

The statistics of the social media			
The social media	Followers	Number of the posts	Topics of the posts
Instagram	622	162 posts	Mainly, the posts are dedicated to the main achievements (deliverables, milestones, webinars, activities, projects, etc.) by all alliance partners of the project. Note that the LinkedIn and Twitter profiles are shared with SEA EU Alliance.
Facebook	17	162 posts	
X (Twitter)	1182	908 posts	
LinkedIn	1759	94 posts	

The statistics of the social media of the reSEArch-EU demonstrated that:

- The insights of @research.eu on Instagram show significant results proving the visibility of the held activities and the scientific and educational content with the following data: +36,4% accounts reached, 180% account engagement, 622 total followers and 162 publications.
- The influence on Twitter has been 1.57M (+72.27K) with 1182 followers.
- LinkedIn has 7.5 K of impressions per year with 1759 followers.

All these analytics were taken at the time of the submission of the report.

7.3 Newsletter

All activities, resources and results have been shared with our subscribers in the SEA EU Alliance newsletter.

This is an example of one of the latest newsletters that have been sent.

SEA-INNOVATE HUB

The SEA-INNOVATE HUB is a platform for cooperation through new approaches between scientists and business stakeholders to pursue new innovative solutions to contemporary societal challenges.

[READ MORE](#)

ReSEArch EU Marketplace Tool ready to connect experts with researchers and viceversa

The Marketplace tool has been structured to serve the specific needs and goals of both businesses and academia.

[READ MORE](#)

The SEA EU Academy is ready to welcome its students

It is envisioned as an entirely virtual learning environment promoting regular virtual training, webinars, and seminars.

[READ MORE](#)

The Citizen-Science competition 'Challenges from Cadiz to the World' at the University of Cadiz finish with the Award ceremony

'The activity Citizen Science Contest is finalized with the awards of the competition 'Challenges from Cadiz to the World' at the International Welcome Center of the University of Cadiz

[READ MORE](#)

Matching research strengths with societal challenges SEA-EU alliance

The report summarising the overall vision of the SEA-EU on the main societal challenges in research and innovation was successfully prepared and written.

[READ MORE](#)

In this link, you can find all the newsletters where information about the reSEArch EU project has been included:

<https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/>

7.4 Scientific Projects

Knowing the great research of excellence that is carried out in all the universities of the Alliance, the reSEArch EU project has been used as a loudspeaker for the citizen science

projects that have been developed within the framework of the alliance during these years.

In this sense a website page was created for comply all these citizen science project: <https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/citizen-science-projects/>

And also, citizen science projects were published in the social media accounts to reach a general audience and multiply its scope.

Examples of Citizen Science Project Publications in Social Media

7.5 Public events and webinars organized

To complement all the dissemination of the activities and materials created in the project, different activities open to the public and series webinars (SEA EU Talent) were carried out in the different universities of the alliance.

7.5.1 Participation in the European Researchers Night (ERN)

The European Researchers' Night takes place yearly, typically starting on the last Friday of the month of September, and is the occasion for a Europe-wide public and media event for the promotion of research careers, in particular towards young people and their families.

During the European Researchers' Night (ERN), Universities members of the Alliance held different activities, workshops and exhibitions.

Workshop for children: carving colors (Prof. Hauke Schramm, University of Applied Sciences Kiel).

One of the stations of the chemical field game entitled 'Protect the Environment', in which visitors could learn about environmental protection (UG).

More information about ERN is available in the project website: <https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/european-researcher-nights-in-research-eu-universities/>

7.5.2 Science Activities in relaxed atmosphere

Representatives of different research groups shared their recent and impactful findings talking about their research projects in bars or other emblematic public places to popularize SEA-EU achievements in a relaxed atmosphere.

Speak searching activity in Brest, BEAJ KAFE

Science Cafe: 'Are we facing the end of the world?' (UG)

In this link all the activities in the relaxed atmosphere are available:
<https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/talks-research-relaxed-atmosphere/>

7.5.3 Webinars and Talks by videoconference

As part of the dissemination and the face-to-face activities, the SEA-EU Talent programme is developed with the aim of promoting the work of the SEA-EU Alliance's young researchers, thus increasing the social impact of their investigations and giving a boost to their careers.

It has carried out different thematic sessions with several webinars in each one:

- Food Security: https://youtu.be/2mCW_xFQ0r8
- Human Health: <https://youtu.be/gtZ0StD30s8>
- Migration and human rights: <https://youtu.be/IYwg2A0m7fQ>
- Environmental Pollution: <https://youtu.be/IHIM4Cif5Ko>
- Coastal Management: <https://youtu.be/jzTNDrVrWes>
- Climate change: <https://youtu.be/-bsdvtDUAQ>
- Blue Growth: https://youtu.be/_tv6tmUfJRQ
- Social : <https://youtu.be/aEQjKDLjRe8>

Examples of dissemination material for social media for SEA EU Talent Webinars

7.5.4 Final Event Documentary

Behind the knowledge, research, innovation and development, there are people who can bring the messages of dissemination and usefulness to society much closer to home. For this purpose, at the end of this project, we develop a joint final event to show the results of the reSEArch EU project through the voice of selected protagonists (researchers, associated partners and other stakeholders, students, society).

The event was conducted with a similar format to the TEDx Talks (both in time and agility), in the sense that it celebrated a great virtual party of knowledge and connection with society.

In order to disseminate this activity, a **documentary** has been made, summarizing the contents of the final joint event. This documentary can be used in film screenings in

partner countries for public engagement events. The idea is to share this dissemination activity with the remaining Alliances involved in this SwafS call (and joined through the Forum of European Universities, FOREU). In fact, alliances selected were also invited to join us.

This event and the **dissemination materials** aim to inspire future generations of students and researchers, encouraging them to aspire to become members of European Universities and lead the way towards dreaming a new knowledge, research and innovation landscape for Europe.

More information about the event is available in our website:

<https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/research-eu-closing-joint-event/>

7.6 Broadcast channel - Video Capsules

On our YouTube channel ([SEA-EU European University of the Seas - YouTube](#)), shared with SEA EU Alliance, we have several playlists dedicated to all the activities and materials that have been generated from our project.

This channel has allowed us to reach a general and very varied audience, as well as to do live webinar broadcasts on different research topics, open science, etc.

One of the first materials is to the **“Promotion of Open Science practice”** in order to identify ‘best practices’ in Open Science throughout the SEA-EU Alliance. For this identification a series of [6 video capsules for academics](#) (one per SEA-EU university, M24-36) featuring success stories and explaining the benefits of Open Science as it

relates to research uptake. It has been conducted by the Open Science Ambassadors, who have a key role in the identification of best practices.

Promotion of Open Science Practice - List of video capsules in our YouTube Channel

<https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLMvtEOr--T7MVqIPHueqGV64ko5AgQF2w&si=E46KsYi0VYthSuE4>

On the other hand, in order to value and make visible **SEA-EU's talented researchers** (SEA- EU Talent) a series of videos (1 per university) where each partner will showcase the activity of two-three top research groups and how the project has impacted their research were recorded.

Promotion of SEA-EU's talented researchers - List of video capsules in our YouTube Channel

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLMvtEOr--T7OgqSTNC2og8e0cE_mQcbbk

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The statistics of the SEA EU Alliance Channel with the reSEArch-EU materials demonstrated that:

The social media	Subscribers	Number of the views	Topics of the videos related to reSEArch EU
YouTube	238	23.401 views/year	1) Webinars of Spin Off Competence Lab 2) Webinars of SEA-EU Talent 3) Video Capsules of Open Science 4) Videos of the pilot activity Citizen Science contest 5) Videos Capsules of SEA EU Talent Researchers

7.7 Additional dissemination activities and materials

In addition to all the dissemination through our own channels and the general face-to-face activities, we have carried out different actions to try to reach different audiences with the project.

7.7.1 Inclusion in the EU-Citizen Science platform

One of the most relevant has been to ask for inclusion in the European citizen science platform ([EU-Citizen.Science](#)) where we have been accepted.

reSEArch-EU

U3O

CIAU

University of Gdansk

University of Split

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017454

eu-citizen.science

We are pleased to let you know that your project [reSEArch-EU](#) has now been moderated and approved. It is now visible in platform search results, and is marked as moderated.

You can make updates or changes to this resource profile at any time, by going to the [Submissions section in your Personal Area](#) (see the top-right of the platform menu).

The EU-CITIZEN.SCIENCE Team

Thanks!

EU-Citizen.Science is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science – by the community, for the community.

The vision for the platform is to serve as a Knowledge Hub, in aid of the mainstreaming of citizen science, and build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific inquiry. We accomplish this by supporting the sharing of knowledge, know-how, and experience between anyone doing or wanting to do citizen science. The EU-Citizen.Science project has been funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 programme, in the Science with and for Society programme of work (also known as SwafS). The project's mission is ambitious – to become the reference point for citizen science through cross-network knowledge sharing for citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society across Europe and reSEArch EU project is already there.

The link to our project in EU-Citizen.Science is: <https://eu-citizen.science/project/450>

7.7.2 Creation of additional dissemination materials

On the other hand posters about our project and different dissemination materials were designed and printed to spread out the scope and the results of reSEArch EU project in the face-to-face events along these years.

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CAIU

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reSEArch-EU

UCA

Universidad de Cádiz

U3O

Universidad de Burgos

CAU

Universidad de Cantabria

University of Gdansk

University of Split

L-Università ta' Malta

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reSEArch-EU

U3O

CAU

University of Gdańsk

University of Split

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8. Quality self-assessment · Performance indicators and measurement tools

In order to ensure the effectiveness of the communication strategy all the activities were quantified using performance indicators and measurement tools.

The annex at table 1 lists both the performance indicators and the measurement tools implemented for each WP.

Table 1

reSEArch-EU activities	Communication tools	KPIs	Target	Measurement of success of communication activities
<p>Anti-fragility think tank (WP2)</p>	<p>Publication Website page Social Media Live Streaming Newsletter</p>	<p>1 live stream: SEA-EU Anti-Fragility Think-Tank: Impact of a pandemic on the university ecosystem 1 website page updated: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/2022-12-20-D-2.1.-AFTT-rules-of-procedure-and-key-areas-of-impact-V2.pdf Permanent coverage https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/thinktank/ 2NL entries: Entry 1: https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/new-sletter-october-22-english-2-compressed.pdf // Entry 2: https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/new-sletter-english-december-</p>	<p>EU Universities Other Alliances Stakeholders Management Researchers</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of reactions and views - 120 views</p>

		<p>21_compressed.pdf Social Media: https://www.instagram.com/p/CsBR2GnRv2y/?img_index=1</p>		
<p>Development of roadmap for digital transformation of R&I (WP2)</p>	<p>Publication Website page Social Media Newsletter</p>	<p>1 Open Access Publication: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/2022-12-20-D2.2-Digital-transformation-of-research-and-innovation-roadmap-v5.pdf</p> <p>2NL entries: https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Copy-of-newsletter-julio-22-english_compressed.pdf</p> <p>Social Media Examples: https://www.instagram.com/p/Cpunbwsox0N/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/Cq2tsikIVJc/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/CrLUBcVRsqV/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/CrdH8dYN6HX/</p>	<p>EU Universities Other Alliances Stakeholders Management Researchers</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of reactions and views - more than 225 accounts reached in the different social networks</p>
<p>Remote work/remotization of infrastructure for R&I</p>	<p>Publication Website page</p>	<p>1 web site news https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2</p>	<p>EU Universities Other Alliances</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available</p>

<p>(WP2)</p>	<p>Social Media Newsletter</p>	<p>022/04/D2.3_Remote-work-and-remotization-of-infrastructure-case-study_v1_final.pdf 2NL entries: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/ Social Media Examples:https://www.instagram.com/p/CyvSpBRNZMK/ https://www.instagram.com/p/CzBbBBcIWIA/</p>	<p>Stakeholders Management Researchers</p>	<p>Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of reactions and views - more than 246 accounts reached in the different social networks</p>
<p>SEA EU Academy pilot project (WP2)</p>	<p>Website page Brochure Social Media Minimum 3 NL entries</p>	<p>1 website page: https://academy.sea-eu.org/ Permanent coverage: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/noticia/presentation-of-the-guiding-principles-for-the-sea-eu-academy/ Virtual Teaching space: https://academy.sea-eu.org/ launch: https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/new</p>	<p>Researchers Support Staff</p>	<p>Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of reactions - more than 125 accounts reached in the different social networks Requests for information - not available</p>

		<p>sletter-english-december-21-compressed.pdf, experiences (https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Copy-of-newsletter-julio-22-english-compressed.pdf), result (https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/)</p> <p>Social Media Examples: Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/p/Co4p5Hto_6G/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/CpKdfRZIUOM/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/CpcYHuloLke/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/CpunbwsxoN/</p>		
<p>Greening research and innovation practices (WP2)</p>	<p>Position Paper Specialized Media Traditional Media Social Media Minimum 2NL entries</p>	<p>1 Publication: Public Report: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/2022-06-30-Position-Paper-Greening-Research.pdf</p> <p>NL entries: https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Cop</p>	<p>Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available Number of reactions - more than 141 accounts reached in the different social networks Request for information - not available</p>

<p>Innovative and entrepreneurial potential of SEA EU (WP3)</p>	<p>Report 1NL entry</p>	<p>y-of-newsletter-julio-22-english_compressed.pdf Social media: https://www.instagram.com/p/CoUtdigqm1f/ // https://www.instagram.com/p/ComorFwoZEvl/</p>	<p>Report (or part of it) available on the website: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/2022-12-20-D3.1.-Summary-report-on-the-Innovative-and-Entrepreneurial-potential-of-the-SEA-V2.pdf Social media: https://www.instagram.com/p/CydRHmxNjyb/?img_index=1</p> <p>Minimum 1 entry on newsletter: availability of report: https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/new-sletter-english-december-21_compressed.pdf 1 web page new: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/</p>	<p>Research Associated partners Stakeholders</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available</p>
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<p>Spin-off competence lab training programme (WP3)</p>	<p>Website page Specialized media Traditional media Social Media Minimum 3 NL entries</p>	<p>org/sea-innovate-hub/1 web site news: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/noticia/kick-off-meeting-for-the-sea-innovate-hub/</p>	<p>Early Stage researchers Stakeholders</p>	
		<p>Report: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Science-Shop-Results-1.pdf Website page: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/spin-off-competence-lab-2/ Social media example: https://www.instagram.com/researcheu/guide/spin-off-competence-lab/17995573481186849/ Permanent coverage: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/spin-off-competence-lab-2/ 3NL entries: launch https://sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Copy-of-newsletter-julio-22-en</p>		<p>Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of reactions - more than 231 accounts reached in the different social networks Request for information - not available</p>

		<p>glish_compressed.pdf , experiences https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/, results https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/</p>		
<p>Workshops and online guide for transdisciplinarity (WP4)</p>	<p>Website page Social media Brochure 1 NL entry per workshop</p>	<p>Post and photos of the workshops available on the website: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/workshops-and-online-guide-for-transdisciplinarity/ 1 brochure available on the website: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gsu8QdHJpiMRgOpeFOYerbKTEly0rvwt1/view</p>	<p>Students Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders</p>	<p>Number of participants - 32 participants Number of visitor to website - non available Number of post and photos published 6 Number of reactions - non applicable.</p>
<p>Pilot activities on Market Place, Transformation Labs, Science Shops and Citizen Science Contests (WP4)</p>	<p>Website page Brochure Social Media Traditional media (press, radio, TV)</p>	<p>Post and photos/ videos of activities available on the website: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/pilot-activities/ 1 press release: https://www.uca.es/noticia</p>	<p>Students Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders All the society</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of post and photos/ videos published - more than 20 photos and</p>

	<p>1 entry NL per activity</p>	<p>/abierto-el-plazo-del-concurso-retos-de-cadiz-al-mundo/</p> <p>1 brochure with all the activities: https://rechercheu.sea-eu.org/pilot-activities/</p> <p>NL: https://rechercheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/</p> <p>Social Media Instagram examples: Social Media: Instagram: Citizen Science Contest (UCA): https://www.instagram.com/m/p/CsS1Ay4IKYE/ Transformation lab UBO: https://www.instagram.com/m/p/CnjrefEg4vp/ Science Shop (UG): https://www.instagram.com/m/p/CrveCTWRZ_9/ // https://www.instagram.com/m/p/CrTgUoYRekA/ // https://www.instagram.com/m/p/Cr-0Ks4x1ZT/ // https://www.instagram.com/m/p/CsGUhcAXZS5/ // https://www.instagram.com/m/p/CsI5VQuRtLG/ //</p>		<p>post were published</p> <p>Number of reactions: more than 1245 reached accounts</p> <p>Number of participants: more than 127 participants in all the pilot activities</p>
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<p>SEA-EU Open Data System, Open Science Ambassadors programme (WP5)</p>	<p>Social media Specialized media 1 entry on newsletter</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/p/CsoDxi7xQBZ/ Transformation LAB CAU: https://www.instagram.com/p/Cr01Vz4RWDd/</p> <p>Diffusion of ambassador's profiles website: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/meet-the-sea-eu-open-science-ambassadors/ Face-to-face activities: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/open-science-staff-week-cadiz-meeting/</p>	<p>Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders</p>	<p>Number of reactions more than 78 reached account in the social media Requests for information - not available</p>
<p>Digest paper on main challenges facing SEA-EU community (WP6)</p>	<p>Paper 1 NL entry</p>	<p>1 publication: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/reSEArch-EU-Deliverable-6.1-Digest-EEC-20230608.pdf 1 press release on website: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/noticia/matching-research-strengths-with-societal-challenges-sea-eu-alliance/</p>	<p>Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders</p>	<p>Number of readings and downloads - not available Number of reactions - more than 68 reached accounts in social media Requests for information - not available</p>

<p>SEA-EU Talent video series, webinar and informal talks (WP7)</p>		<p>NL :https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/</p> <p>Social media: https://www.instagram.com/p/Cu4UQv9lANA/?img_index=1</p>		
<p>Social media Website page Poster Brochures 1 NL entry with dates 1NL entry to advertise the video series</p>		<p>1 attractive poster with talks dates: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/sea-eu-talent-meet-ou-t-participants/</p> <p>6 videos: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/sea-eu-talent-video-capsules/</p> <p>1 brochure per event: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/talks-research-relaxed-atmosphere/</p> <p>Permanent coverage: https://www.instagram.com/stories/highlights/17885387522768378/</p> <p>NL entry: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/newsletter-sea-eu-research-eu/</p>	<p>All the society</p>	<p>Number of visitor to website - 26.352 per year</p> <p>Number of video visualization - more than 421 views in all the videos</p> <p>Number of participant - 160 participants</p>

<p>Mid-term meeting of the Forum of European Universities (FOREU) (WP7)</p>	<p>Report Social media Website page Specialized media Poster 2NL entries</p>	<p>1 report: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/cross-alliances-forum-2023/ 1 poster announcing the event: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/cross-alliances-forum-2023/ 1 press release on website: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/noticia/ri-in-european-universities-alliances-cross-alliances-forum-2023/</p>	<p>Student Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders Other Alliances All the society</p>	<p>Number of participants - 226 registered Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of readings and downloads - not available</p>
<p>Video capsules best practices Open Science (WP5, WP7)</p>	<p>Social media Website page (1-6 entries on newsletter depending on the release of capsules)</p>	<p>6 video capsules: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/open-science-videocapsules/ Social Media YouTube and Instagram examples: // https://www.instagram.com/researcheu/guide/open-science-videocapsules/18001168478115611/</p>	<p>Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders</p>	<p>Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of visualization - more than 523 views</p>

<p>Joint end of the project webinar with all European Universities and documentary (WP7)</p>	<p>Report Social Media Website page Specialized media Poster 2NL entries</p>	<p>1 report: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/research-eu-closing-joint-event/ 1 poster announcing the event https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/research-eu-closing-joint-event/ 1 press release on website: announcement: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/noticia/research-eu-closing-joint-event-2023/ After the event: https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/noticia/closing-joint-event-if-the-research-eu-project-research-and-innovation-in-the-sea-eu-university-alliance/ 1 documentary https://researcheu.sea-eu.org/research-eu-closing-joint-event/ 1 press release https://cadiznoticias.es/el-proyecto-research-eu-de-l</p>	<p>Student Researchers Associated partners Stakeholders Other Alliances All the society</p>	<p>Number of participants - 59 participants physically Number of readings and downloads - not available Number of visitors to website - 26.352 per year Number of documentary visualization - not available yet</p>
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